

A survey for the invasive ant *Lasius cf. niger* on Nantucket Island

Robert D. Stevenson, Tim Lynam, Luiz Rodrigues, Emily Clark and Charles Defarias

Dept. of Biology, UMass Boston, 100 Morrissey Blvd., Boston, MA 02125-3393

Contact: robert.stevenoson@umb.edu tel. 617-287-6500, cell 978-270-6444, fax 617-297-6650

Abstract

Ant surveys on Tuckernuck and Muskeget islands in 2013 revealed 5 new species including the invasive species *Lasius cf. niger*. *Lasius cf. niger* has been found before in New England but only sporadically. Our 2013 surveys found it to be the 4th most common ant by number on Tuckernuck and the second most common ant on Muskeget (Stevenson et al 2014). This ant species was not previously reported in Ellison's (2012) synthesis of ant records for Nantucket Island. Given its relative abundance in our 2013 samples, especially in dune areas, we predicted that *Lasius cf. niger* would be found on Nantucket dune habitats. In the seven dune habitats we sampled around Nantucket Island, we found *Lasius cf. niger* to be the most common ant at each site. It was absent at 2 upland sites where we sampled. Genetic tests are needed to determine if the morphotype *Lasius cf. niger* is truly *Lasius niger*.

Introduction

Ellison (2012) recently described the ant fauna of Nantucket Island based on 384 samples collected from 2000 to 2009. He found 58 species which represents about 50% of the species and 70% of the genera found in all of New England. In 2013 we sampled Tuckernuck and Muskeget Islands which were still united with Nantucket just 2500-3000 years ago (Gutierrez et al 2003) and found 38 and 7 species respectively. One of our unanticipated findings was the observation of *Lasius cf. niger*. Ellison et al (2012, p. 204) lists *Lasius cf. niger* as a distinct species from *Lasius neoniger*, which is a well established species in North America. *Lasius cf. niger* had only been collected recently in the summer of 2011 by Pat Kearns an undergraduate student at UMass Boston, while he was working in Sippewissett salt marsh near Falmouth MA. Subsequently Stefan Cover, curator of Harvard's MCZ ant collection, identified the ant as distinct from *Lasius neoniger* and most similar in his opinion to *Lasius niger* a species widely distributed in Europe, Asia and the western USA. This observation led Ellison (2012 p 340-341) to list *Lasius cf. niger* as one of the 14 non-native species of ants in New England.

In 2013 we found almost 600 specimens of *Lasius cf. niger*. It was the second most common of seven species on Muskeget and the fifth most common species of 33 on Tuckernuck. On both islands it was very common on sand dunes where more than two-thirds of the total specimens were found. *Lasius cf. niger* was found on four of five transects on Muskeget and seven of ten transects on Tuckernuck. These findings stimulated many additional questions, one of which we address here.

Is *Lasius cf. niger* found on Nantucket? To study this question we proposed two approaches. First to look in the collections to see if specimens previously identified as *Lasius neoniger* are actually *Lasius cf. niger*. This turned out to be the case with a specimen that Aaron Ellison had obtained from Andrew McKenna-Foster. This specimen was collected on Muskeget and IDed by Stefan Cover. Upon re-examination all agree that this specimen is not *Lasius neoniger* but instead *Lasius cf. niger*. This specimen was collected in 2006 so we know *Lasius cf. niger* has on the East Coast at least 5 years before its presence has been recognized. Our second approach was to sample a variety of habitats on Nantucket focusing on habitats that have lots of open sand cover such as found in dune areas.

We had planned to characterize the status of *Laisus cf. niger* colonies on Tuckernuck and Nantucket. However, time and available resources for field research did not permit investigation of this question.

Methods and study sites

Field sampling: We sampled Low Beach Road, Surfside Beach, Dionis Beach, North Pond Rd and Field Station Beach from June 16th-19th, 2014 and Coskata-Coatue Wildlife Refuge, Coatue Great Point Rd, Almanac Pond Rd and the UMB Field Station field from August 21th- 24th, 2014 (Table1).

We used pit traps and baits, two of four recommended sampling methods in the Ants Leaf Litter (ALL) protocol (Agosti and Alonso 2000, Ipser et al. 2004, Ellison et al 2007, Ellison 2012). The ALL protocol prescribes taking hand and litter samples. However, dune habitats had almost no leaf litter. Due to time constraints we did not do any hand sampling, although experience shows this will increase the diversity of species found.

The details of field sampling were as follows. At each site twenty pitfall traps (500 ml plastic jars with screw tops) were set ten meters apart in a relatively straight line. (There were two exceptions to this layout: at the Almanac Pond Rd site there was a slight bend in the transect to stay in grassland habitat and at the UMB field station meadow site we looped the transects to cover the field.) In order to prevent propylene glycol from evaporating from pit traps and to keep dew and rain water out we used cardboard roofs fixed above the pit trap made from metal stakes and rubber bands. The traps were set for 24 to 48 hours. Next to each pitfall trap we also laid out baits. We alternately placed one-half of a crumbed short bread cookie or a spoonful of canned tuna packed in oil about half a meter away from the pitfall trap and flagged to make them easier to find. The baits were checked the same day at least three to six hours after they had been laid out. Ants were collected at bait sites by hand or with a pooter (aspirator) and stored in plastic centrifuge tubes secured with plastic tops containing o-ring seals.

Lab work: Samples were cleaned in the lab and sorted using dissecting microscopes. Specimens stored in vials with 90% ethanol. Representative ant species were deposited at the Harvard Museum of Comparative Zoology in Cambridge.

Species identification: Ants were identified using [A Field Guide to the Ants of New England](#) (Ellison et al. 2012). Stefan Cover, the curator of the ant collection at the Harvard University Museum of Comparative Zoology, checked and corrected our identifications.

Analysis: The number of ants of each species was counted in each pitfall and bait trap. Data were entered into a Google Doc spreadsheet and summarized using pivot-tables. (The data table is available upon request).

Results

Lasius cf. niger was found in abundance at the seven dune sites: Coatue Great Point Rd, Coskata-Coatue Wildlife Refuge, Dionis Beach, Field Station Beach, Low Beach Road, North Pond Rd, and Surfside Beach (Table 1, Table 2). Of the 13 species we found at these 7 dune habitat locations (all but Almanac Pond Rd. and the UMass Field Station Field sites), *Lasius cf. niger* was the only species found at all 7 sites and it was the most common ant we found. Of the 360 bait and pit traps we set, *Lasius cf. niger* was found in 170 or 47 % of these (Table 2) and 60% of the dune traps and of the 2536 ants we counted *Lasius cf. niger* totaled 67% (Table 3) from the all the habitats but more significantly 74% of the individuals from the dune habitat. When compared to bait traps, pit traps were more successful at capturing *Lasius cf. niger* accounting for about 60% of the successful traps and 85% of the individuals collected (Table 4).

After *Lasius cf. niger*, *Formica argentea* and *Solenopsis cf. texana* were the next most abundant species based on the number of sites (5) at which the species was observed (Table 2), followed by *Formica subsericea*, *Lasius alienus*, and *Tetramorium caespitum* all of which were observed at 4 sites. *Tetramorium caespitum* was the second most abundant ant species observed (Table 3).

We found a total of 17 species across 9 sites but interestingly there were only between four to six species found at each site (Table 2). Four species *Aphaenogaster rudis*, *Formica creightoni*, *Monomorium emarginatum*, *Myrmica incomplete*, were observed only on the upland sites at Almanac Pond Road and the UMB Field Station field.

Discussion

Although unknown from previous samples on Nantucket (Ellison 2012), *Lasius cf. niger* is now the spatially and numerically dominant ant species in dune habitats of the island (Table 2, Table 3)

Comparison between the ant species found in beach/dune habitats from Ellison (2012, data from archive) with the present study (Table 5) suggests that *Lasius cf. niger* has replaced *L. neoniger* as the dominant species. *L. neoniger* makes up 48% of the individuals in the Ellison (2012) sample and *Lasius cf. niger* is unobserved, while *L. neoniger* makes up less than 1% of the individuals in the present study and *Lasius cf. niger* makes up 74% (Table 5).

Both studies found a total of 13 species but they share only 6 species. Our present study shares six species in common with those reported by Ellison (2012) (Table 5). The lack of overlap in species composition speaks to the dynamic nature of these ant communities and perhaps equally to the need for more comprehensive sampling because of the difficulty of detecting ant species (Clark et al 2011).

Preliminary observations on Cape Cod suggest that *Lasius cf. niger* is abundant in dune habitats on the mainland. These data taken together suggest this new species is replacing *Lasius neoniger*.

These studies have been conducted in close consultation with Aaron Ellison at Harvard Forest and Stefan Cover at Harvard's MCZ. Ellison is the first author of the A Field Guide to the Ants of New England while Cover is recognized as one of the most knowledgeable and experienced

ant scientists in the Western Hemisphere. Both agree that genetic data are needed to provide more information about the morphotype *Lasius cf. niger* and its origins.

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Table 1. GPS coordinates for the start and end points of transects at nine sites sampled for ants with bait and pit traps on Nantucket Island in 2014. The first five sites were sampled between June 16th-19th and the last four sites between August 21th- 24th.

Island	Location	Transect Name	Start Coordinates		End Coordinates		Description
			Location N	Location W (-)	Location N	Location W (-)	
Nantucket	Low Beach Road	A	41.2521	-69.9680	41.2508	-69.9700	Dune habitat
Nantucket	Surfside Beach	B	41.2434	-70.0943	41.2439	-70.0920	Dune habitat
Nantucket	Dionis Beach	C	41.2932	-70.1529	41.2929	-70.1554	Dune habitat
Nantucket	North Pond Rd	D	41.2935	-70.1827	41.2934	-70.1803	Dune habitat
Nantucket	Field Station Beach	E	41.2957	-70.0416	41.2950	-70.0439	Dune habitat
Nantucket	Coskata-Coatue Wildlife Refuge	F	41.3632	-70.0179	41.3645	-70.0188	Dune habitat
Nantucket	Coatue Great Point Rd	G	41.3583	-70.0146	41.3598	-70.0157	Dune habitat
Nantucket	Almanac Pond Rd ¹	H	41.2873	-70.0085	41.2860	-70.0096	Upland meadow
Nantucket	UMB Field Station Field ²	I	41.2963	-70.0400	41.2961	-79.0386	Meadow

¹ Transect has a slight bend at the end to keep the traps in the grassland habitat

² Traps arranged in loops to cover an area rather than a linear transect

Table 2. Distribution of species at sites and by the number of traps that held them

Species	Almanac Pond Rd	Coatue Great Point Rd	Coskata- Coatue Wildlife Refuge	Dionis Beach	Field Station Beach	Low Beach Road	North Pond Rd	Surfside Beach	UMB Field Station Field	Total no. of traps with species	No of sites with species
<i>Aphaenogaster rudis</i>									18	18	1
<i>Crematogaster lineolata</i>				7	6					13	2
<i>Formica argentea</i>		6	3		2	4		7		22	5
<i>Formica creightoni</i>	4									4	1
<i>Formica subaenescens</i>						2				2	1
<i>Formica subsericea</i>	2	1	6					1		10	4
<i>Lasius alienus</i>	1					3		6	1	11	4
<i>Lasius cf. niger</i>		26	26	21	14	29	21	33		170	7
<i>Lasius claviger</i>					1					1	1
<i>Lasius flavus</i>				1			2			3	2
<i>Lasius latipes</i>							4	1		5	2
<i>Lasius neoniger</i>		2	2							4	2
<i>Monomorium emarginatum</i>	2								2	4	2
<i>Myrmica incompleta</i>	1								3	4	2
<i>Solenopsis cf. texana</i>		2		2	3			4	2	13	5
<i>Tapinoma sessile</i>				2			2			4	2
<i>Tetramorium caespitum</i>	29		1		12	4				46	4
No. species per site	6	5	5	5	6	5	4	6	5		

Table 3. Number of individuals of different species captured at each site.

Species	Almanac Pond Rd	Coatue Great Point Rd	Coskata- Coatue Wildlife Refuge	Dionis Beach	Field Station Beach	Low Beach Road	North Pond Rd	Surfside Beach	UMB Field Station Field	Total
<i>Aphaenogaster rudis</i>									58	58
<i>Crematogaster lineolata</i>				27	18					45
<i>Formica argentea</i>		8	16		5	8		15		52
<i>Formica creightoni</i>	4									4
<i>Formica subaenescens</i>						49				49
<i>Formica subsericea</i>	2	1	14					1		18
<i>Lasius alienus</i>	1					7		12	1	21
<i>Lasius cf. niger</i>		126	234	243	70	241	225	577		1716
<i>Lasius claviger</i>					9					9
<i>Lasius flavus</i>				0			12			12
<i>Lasius latipes</i>							20	3		23
<i>Lasius neoniger</i>		5	12							17
<i>Monomorium emarginatum</i>	105								16	121
<i>Myrmica incompleta</i>	4								6	10
<i>Solenopsis cf. texana</i>		2		3	5			10	13	33
<i>Tapinoma sessile</i>				5			3			8
<i>Tetramorium caespitum</i>	241		1		76	22				340
Total	357	142	285	278	183	327	260	618	94	2536

Table 4. Distribution of species and number of individuals by trap type.

Species	Number of Traps				Number of Individuals				
	Bait trap	Pit trap	Total traps	Bait traps/Pit traps	Bait trap	Pit trap	Total Individuals	No of individuals per trap	Individuals by Bait/Individuals by Pit
<i>Aphaenogaster rudis</i>	13	5	18	2.6	43	15	58	3.2	2.9
<i>Crematogaster lineolata</i>	5	8	13	0.6	17	28	45	3.5	0.6
<i>Formica argentea</i>	18	4	22	4.5	43	9	52	2.4	4.8
<i>Formica creightoni</i>		4	4			4	4	1.0	
<i>Formica subaenescens</i>		2	2			49	49	24.5	
<i>Formica subsericea</i>	2	8	10	0.3	6	12	18	1.8	0.5
<i>Lasius latipes</i>		1	1			1	1	1.0	
<i>Lasius alienus</i>		11	11			21	21	1.9	
<i>Lasius cf. niger</i>	61	109	170	0.6	275	1440	1715	10.1	0.2
<i>Lasius claviger</i>		1	1			9	9	9.0	
<i>Lasius flavus</i>		3	3			12	12	4.0	
<i>Lasius latipes</i>		4	4			22	22	5.5	
<i>Lasius neoniger</i>	3	1	4	3.0	10	7	17	4.3	1.4
<i>Monomorium emarginatum</i>	1	3	4	0.3	12	109	121	30.3	0.1
<i>Myrmica incompleta</i>	1	3	4	0.3	4	6	10	2.5	0.7
<i>Solenopsis cf. texana</i>	1	12	13	0.1	9	24	33	2.5	0.4
<i>Tapinoma sessile</i>	1	3	4	0.3	1	7	8	2.0	0.1
<i>Tetramorium caespitum</i>	8	38	46	0.2	58	282	340	7.4	0.2

Table 5. Comparison between the ant species found in beach/dune habitats from Ellison 2012 with the present study which sampled dunes but not beaches. *Lasius cf. niger* seems to have replace *L. neoniger* as the dominate species based on the % in the sample. Both studies found a total of 13 species but they share only 6 species.

Subfamily	Species	Ellison 2012		this study	
		Abundance	%	Abundance	%
Ponerinae	<i>Ponera pennsylvanica</i>	4	3.70		
Dolichiderinae	<i>Tapinoma sessile</i>	4	3.70	8	0.35
Formicidae	<i>Formica argentea</i>			52	2.24
	<i>Formica incerta</i>	1	0.93		
	<i>Formica subaenescens</i>			49	2.11
	<i>Formica subsericea</i>	14	12.96	18	0.78
	<i>Lasius alienus</i>	1	0.93	21	0.91
	<i>Lasius claviger</i>			9	0.39
	<i>Lasius flavus</i>	3	2.78	12	0.52
	<i>Lasius latipes</i>			23	0.99
	<i>Lasius neoniger</i>	48	44.44	17	0.73
	<i>Lasius cf. niger</i>			1716	74.03
	<i>Lasius subglaber</i>	1	0.93		
<i>Nylanderia parvula</i>	1	0.93			
Myrmicinae	<i>Aphaenogaster rudis</i>	5	4.63		
	<i>Crematogaster lineolata</i>	9	8.33	45	1.94
	<i>Myrmica sp. Af-scu</i>	16	14.81		
	<i>Solenopsis cf. texana</i>			8	0.35
	<i>Tetramorium caespitum</i>	1	0.93	340	14.67
	Total Species Observed	13	13	13	13
Total Numbers Observed	108	100	2318	100	